

THE COMPARISON OF LPT AND THREE-DIMENSIONAL
STRESS DISTRIBUTIONS FOR A
LAMINATED PLATE CONTAINING A HOLE⁺

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Laminated plate theory (LPT) and three-dimensional stress distributions are compared for 12 different laminated plates. Each plate has a circular hole and is loaded in tension. The lay-up angles are described by $(0_2/\pm\theta/\mp\theta)_S$, $(\pm\theta/\mp\theta/0_2)_S$, $(90_2/\pm\theta/\mp\theta)_S$, and $(\pm\theta/\mp\theta/90_2)_S$ where $\theta = 30^\circ$, 45° , and 90° . Material properties are selected to represent graphite/epoxy laminates. Three-dimensional stress distributions are obtained using the SAP IV three-dimensional finite element analysis. For the cases considered, comparisons of the LPT and SAP IV results show a difference in the tangential stress component around the circular hole that varied between 15% and 50%. Generally, higher stress values were found from the three-dimensional results for the 0° and 90° plies. However, in some cases the LPT solution gave higher values of the tangential stress in the angle plies.

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Introduction

The stress analysis approach commonly used for fiber reinforced laminated plates is based on the laminated plate theory (LPT). A description of the method can be found in many references, for example, see References [1] and [2]. In the LPT models, the out-of-plane stresses are zero and stress boundary conditions at free edges are not satisfied. Because LPT analyses are used in the design of composite structures to predict survivability, it is of interest to know how the LPT stresses compare with the three-dimensional stress distributions. In the far-field regions, away from edges and attachments, the LPT solution is exact for linear elastic behavior. Near free edges, the boundary conditions of the LPT solution are that the resultant force and bending moments on the edges are zero. The LPT model permits nonzero stresses on the laminate free edges while the true boundary conditions are zero normal and shear stresses on these edges.

The work described here is part of a larger study of the free edge effects around circular holes [3]. In this study, the stress distributions around a circular hole were obtained for several laminates using the LPT analysis and a three-dimensional finite element analysis. The LPT solutions were obtained using the effective moduli of the laminate in a two-dimensional solution for an orthotropic plate containing a hole. The stresses obtained from the LPT analysis are resultant stresses representing the average of the stresses in all the plies. Stresses in individual plies can then be evaluated from the LPT distributions by using the conditions that the in-plane strains are the same in all plies. Three-dimensional stress distributions were obtained using the SAP IV Program [4]. Comparisons of the results obtained from the three-dimensional finite element stress analysis and the LPT model were made. These comparisons focus on the tangential stress distributions around a circular hole.

Method of Stress Analysis

The stress analysis is based on a compatible finite element representation for the deformations of a three-dimensional solid. The computer program is SAP IV. Details of this program and the stress analysis method are given in Reference [4]. Only a summary of the stress analysis is given here.

In the finite element stress analysis, laminate plies are modeled as three-dimensional homogeneous orthotropic materials with linear stress-strain behavior. Symmetric laminates are considered. Loading conditions are uniform applied stress distant to the hole. Compatibility conditions within each element and between contiguous elements are satisfied exactly. In this finite element analysis, equilibrium is satisfied approximately.

Some of the laminates that are analyzed have a $(\pm\theta/\mp\theta)$ set of plies. This combination of plies by itself is symmetric and has no extensional-bending or extensional-shear coupling. In the finite element analyses, the $(\pm\theta/\mp\theta)$ plies were represented as a homogeneous material with orthotropic effective modulus properties. This simplification reduced the portion of the plate that had to be modeled. One quarter of the top half of each laminate was modeled. In each case, 36 elements were used as shown in Figure 1. The grid contains three layers of elements through the thickness with 12 elements in each layer. A three-dimensional twenty-node element with corner and midside nodes was used. The three-dimensional stress analysis provides stress results at the node points of the elements.

Fig. 1 - Finite element model for the symmetry section of a laminated plate.

Results

Tangential stress distributions around a circular hole are obtained for several laminates using the LPT model. These results are compared with the tangential stress distributions from the three-dimensional finite element solutions computed with the SAP IV Program. The LPT solutions were evaluated using the effective moduli properties of the laminate in a two-dimensional solution for a tension loaded orthotropic plate containing a hole. The stresses obtained from the orthotropic plate analysis are resultant stresses for the LPT analysis. The stresses in each ply were evaluated from the LPT strain distributions by using the conditions that the inplane strains are the same in all plies. The three-dimensional analyses were performed using the three-dimensional finite element representation described in the previous section. Laminates for this study have the stacking sequence $(0_2/\pm\theta/\mp\theta)_S$, $(\pm\theta/\mp\theta/0_2)_S$, $(90_2/\pm\theta/\mp\theta)_S$, and $(\pm\theta/\mp\theta/90_2)_S$. Values of θ equal to 30° , 45° , and 60° were used in the computations. The material properties used for the LPT and three-dimensional analyses are given in Table 1. The loading is a uniform tension stress in the 0° direction.

In presenting the comparisons, it is pointed out that in the LPT solutions stresses do not vary through the thickness of each ply, interlaminar stresses are zero and for the cases considered here LPT solutions are independent of stacking sequence. This is, however, not representative of the actual mechanical behavior as shown, for example, by Pipes and Pagano [5], Rybicki [6], Pagano [7], and Rybicki and Schmuesser [8]. Thus, a location in the three-dimensional model was selected to compare the three-dimensional calculations with the LPT results. The midplane of the laminate

Table 1. Material Properties^(a) for $(\pm\theta/\bar{+}\theta/0_2)_S$ Laminates

Material Property	Plies			
	0_2°	$(\pm 30/\bar{+}30)$	$(\pm 45/\bar{+}45)$	$(\pm 60/\bar{+}60)$
E_1 (GPa)	151.60	58.88	23.72	14.00
E_2 (GPa)	11.00	14.00	23.72	58.88
E_3 (GPa)	11.00	11.38	11.58	11.38
ν_{12}	.25	1.24	.72	.29
ν_{13}	.25	-.035	.08	.18
ν_{23}	.25	.18	.08	-.035
G_{12} (GPa)	6.89	31.30	39.51	31.30
G_{13} (GPa)	6.89	6.06	5.38	4.83
G_{23} (GPa)	4.41	4.83	5.38	6.06

(a) Values obtained from Reference [9].

Table 2. Three-Dimensional Finite Element Results^(a) and LPT Solutions for Tangential Stress Distributions for $(0_2/\pm 30/\bar{+}30)_S$, $(\pm 30/\bar{+}30/0_2)_S$, $(0_2/\pm 45/\bar{+}45)_S$, and $(\pm 45/\bar{+}45/0_2)_S$ Laminates^(b)

θ	$(\pm 30/\bar{+}30/0_2)_S$ (0_2) Plies		$(0_2/\pm 30/\bar{+}30)_S$ ($\bar{+}30$) Plies	
	Three-Dimensional Analysis	LPT	Three-Dimensional Analysis	LPT
0°	-.3884	-.2835	-.3630	-.4637
13.3°	-.3258	-.2242	-.4746	-.4646
26.6°	-.1250	-.1026	-.2050	-.3892
45.0°	-.5612	.0815	.6258	.3384
63.4°	1.5167	1.7981	1.7874	2.1158
76.7°	4.8991	4.5609	2.2896	2.6173
90.0°	7.2951	5.8391	2.4048	2.5129
θ	$(\pm 45/\bar{+}45/0_2)_S$ (0_2) Plies		$(0_2/\pm 45/\bar{+}45)_S$ ($\bar{+}45$) Plies	
	Three-Dimensional Analysis	LPT	Three-Dimensional Analysis	LPT
0°	-.3846	-.2317	-.5922	-.8749
13.3°	-.3073	-.1631	-.7034	-.8251
26.6°	-.0959	-.0551	-.1773	-.5195
45.0°	-.7164	.2739	.8909	.9065
63.4°	1.8534	3.0262	1.2629	2.0203
76.7°	6.1819	5.6950	1.197	1.5066
90.0°	9.3488	6.7456	.9826	1.1379

(a) Evaluated at laminate midplane.
 (b) Values in the table are divided by the applied stress and are dimensionless.

Table 3. Three-Dimensional Finite Element Results (a)
and LPT Solutions for Tangential Stress
Distributions for $(\pm 60/\mp 60/0_2)_S$, $(0_2/\pm 60/\mp 60)_S$,
 $(\pm 30/\mp 30/90_2)_S$, and $(90_2/\pm 30/\mp 30)_S$ Laminates (b)

θ	$(\pm 60/\mp 60/0_2)_S$ (0 ₂) Plies		$(0_2/\pm 60/\mp 60)_S$ (+60) Plies	
	Three-Dimensional		Three-Dimensional	
	Analysis	LPT	Analysis	LPT
0°	- .3030	- .1715	- 1.1902	- 1.4142
13.3°	- .2243	- .1226	- .9620	- 1.1211
26.6°	- .0056	- .0384	- .1285	- .2778
45.0°	- .6820	.6484	.8530	1.1756
63.4°	2.1189	3.5333	.8207	1.5303
76.7°	6.8667	6.3164	.6745	1.0242
90°	10.3716	7.5932	.5980	.7033
θ	$(\pm 30/\mp 30/90_2)_S$ (90 ₂) Plies		$(90_2/\pm 30/\mp 30)_S$ (+30) Plies	
	Three-Dimensional		Three-Dimensional	
	Analysis	LPT	Analysis	LPT
0°	- 3.2425	- 2.5310	- .1551	- .2344
13.3°	- 2.1903	- 1.7857	- .3373	- .2895
26.6°	- .5072	- .3183	.1587	- .1378
45.0°	.5650	.6486	1.5615	1.1756
63.4°	.4734	.4266	3.0350	3.0837
76.7°	.5845	.4338	3.7326	3.9655
90°	.6312	.5142	3.6397	4.2426

(a) Evaluated at laminate midplane.
(b) Values in the table are divided by the applied stress and are dimensionless.

was selected. The reason for this was that the tangential stresses at this location appeared to take on the largest magnitudes. A summary of comparisons of σ_θ values is given in Tables 2, 3, and 4. Note that because of the midplane selection, the stresses for the $(\pm\theta/\mp\theta)$ plies were evaluated from $(0_2/\pm\theta/\mp\theta)_S$ or $(90_2/\pm\theta/\mp\theta)_S$ laminates while the stresses for the (0_2) and (90_2) plies were evaluated from $(\pm\theta/\mp\theta/0_2)_S$ and $(\pm\theta/\mp\theta/90_2)_S$ laminates.

In looking at Tables 2, 3, and 4, several comparative features are noted. First, in some cases the three-dimensional solutions have the larger values of σ_θ and in other cases, the LPT values are larger. For example, in Table 3 the three-dimensional solution for the 0₂ plies is about 37% larger than the corresponding LPT value at $\theta = 90^\circ$. However, in the same table, the tangential stress in the $(\pm 60/\mp 60)$ plies shows a larger value from the LPT solution than from the three-dimensional solution. Another interesting comparison of these two models is that the peak stress value does not always occur at the 0° or 90° locations. When this happens, as in Table 2 for the $(\pm 45/\mp 45)$ plies, it can occur for both the LPT and three-dimensional results.

The range of the differences of the values for the LPT and three-dimensional models is also of interest. For the 0₂ plies, the three-

Table 4. Three-Dimensional Finite Element Results^(a) and LPT Solutions for Tangential Stress Distributions for $(\pm 45/\pm 45/90_2)_S$, $(90_2/\pm 45/\pm 45)_S$, $(\pm 60/\pm 60/90_2)_S$, and $(90_2/\pm 60/\pm 60)_S$ Laminates^(b)

θ	$(\pm 45/\pm 45/90_2)_S$ (90 ₂) Plies		$(90_2/\pm 45/\pm 45)_S$ (∓ 45) Plies	
	Three-Dimensional Analysis	LPT	Three-Dimensional Analysis	LPT
0°	-5.0800	-3.3959	- .2646	- .5728
13.3°	-3.4731	-2.3695	- .4984	- .6268
26.6°	- .9730	- .2040	.7941	- .1362
45.0°	.9052	.7001	3.0358	2.3171
63.4°	.8656	.3590	3.0363	3.3851
76.7°	1.0930	.6357	2.4902	3.2162
90°	1.2216	.8158	2.2123	3.0808
θ	$(\pm 60/\pm 60/90_2)_S$ (90 ₂) Plies		$(90_2/\pm 60/\pm 60)_S$ (∓ 60) Plies	
	Three-Dimensional Analysis	LPT	Three-Dimensional Analysis	LPT
0°	-5.7912	-3.9941	-1.1889	-1.7187
13.3°	-3.9022	-2.3192	- .7533	- .13309
26.6°	-1.0050	.4136	1.1154	.4867
45.0°	1.3842	.7232	3.1828	3.0020
63.4°	1.4759	.7859	2.5596	2.9797
76.7°	1.8010	1.2314	1.9582	2.5517
90°	1.9957	1.4457	2.0243	2.3647

(a) Evaluated at laminate midplane.
(b) Values in the table are divided by the applied stress and are dimensionless.

dimensional solution is 25% larger than the LPT value for the $(\pm 30/\pm 30/0_2)_S$ laminate shown in Table 2 and about 38% larger for both the $(\pm 45/\pm 45/0_2)_S$ and $(\pm 60/\pm 60/0_2)_S$ laminates shown in Tables 2 and 3. All of the comparisons were taken at the 90° location. The results in Table 3 also show that the three-dimensional stress value in the (90₂) plies of the $(\pm 30/\pm 30/90_2)_S$ laminate is about 30% greater than the LPT value at the $\theta = 0^\circ$ location. However, at the 90° location of the same laminate, the LPT value is about 17% larger than the three-dimensional result. Larger percent differences occur for the $(\pm 45/\pm 45/90_2)_S$ laminate in Table 4. In this case, the three-dimensional analysis is 50% greater than the LPT result at both 0° and 90°. Also note that the maximum tensile value for the $(\pm 45/\pm 45)$ plies is 40% greater for the LPT solution.

Two additional laminates were considered in this study to further illustrate the comparison of three-dimensional finite element results and LPT solutions. The lay-up is denoted by $(0_2/\pm 45/0)_S$ and $(\pm 45/0_2/0)_S$. For this laminate, the properties used for the (± 45) plies and the 0° plies are given in Table 5. Note that the (± 45) plies were represented by a single material with no extensional/bending coupling. Also, the value for ν_{12} of .778 is less than what would be obtained by rotating the properties for the

Table 5. Material Properties Used in Modeling.
 $(0_2/\pm 45/0)_S$ and $(\pm 45/0_2/0)_S$ Laminates

	Modulus (GPa)	Poisson's Ratios	Shear Modulus (GPa)
0° Plies	$E_1 = 206.8$	$\nu_{12} = .21$	$G_{12} = 7.3$
	$E_2 = 18.6$	$\nu_{13} = .24$	$G_{13} = 7.3$
	$E_3 = 18.6$	$\nu_{23} = .25$	$G_{23} = 7.3$
(± 45) Plies	$E_1 = 25.99$	$\nu_{12} = .778$	$G_{12} = 54.6$
	$E_2 = 25.99$	$\nu_{13} = .21$	$G_{13} = 7.3$
	$E_3 = 18.6$	$\nu_{23} = .21$	$G_{23} = 7.3$

0° ply given in Table 5. Nonetheless, these properties have some value in comparing two- and three-dimensional solutions. Figure 2 shows a comparison of the tangential stress distributions obtained from the three-dimensional and two-dimensional analyses for the $(0_2/\pm 45/0)_S$ laminate. These differences are of the same order as those shown in Tables 2, 3, and 4. Figure 3 is of interest also for comparing LPT and three-dimensional results, in that it shows how the tangential stress distribution through the laminate thickness compares with the constant LPT results. Another difference shown in this figure is that the stress concentration for the 0° plies is higher in the three-dimensional analysis than in the two-dimensional analysis.

Fig. 2 - Stress distributions around a hole in a $(0_2/\pm 45/0)_S$ laminate

Fig 3 - Distribution of tangential stress through laminate thickness at $\theta = 90^\circ$

Discussion and Conclusions

A comparison of LPT stress distributions and those obtained from a three-dimensional finite element model showed that there was not always close agreement for the tangential stresses around a circular hole. The percentage difference between the results of the LPT and three-dimensional models used in this study ranged from 15% to 50%. However, it cannot be concluded that similar comparisons for other laminates would give a similar range of percentages. For example, cases where LPT and three-dimensional results were much closer in value were observed when the Poisson's ratios of the plies were closer in value. Specifically, results were obtained (but not shown in this paper) for Poisson's ratios of .3 and .5 in adjacent groups of plies indicated close agreement between LPT and three-dimensional tangential stresses around the circular hole. The comparisons shown here that exhibited larger differences between the LPT and three-dimensional results occurred for Poisson's ratios of .25 and 1.2 for adjacent groups of plies as shown in Table 1.

Generally speaking, another difference between the LPT and three-dimensional results is the value of the interlaminar stresses and the effects of stacking sequence. The interlaminar stresses near the edges of the laminate are always zero in the LPT results. This is not the case for the three-dimensional solutions. Furthermore, these stresses can lead to the initiation of a delamination type of damage. Thus while some modes of

damage for laminated plates may be studied by results of LPT models, there are other modes of damage that need a more sophisticated representation recognizing behavior that the LPT model precludes.

It is emphasized that the differences between the two representations reported here were also based on a specific three-dimensional model described in Figure 1 and a specific finite element analysis. Hence, the three-dimensional results must be viewed in this light. It was previously mentioned that the results of this study cannot be generalized to all laminates. Thus, while there is a need for more work on this topic, this study can be viewed as a first step in addressing a question that is important to designers and stress analysts.

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